

Irenaeus of Lyons, "Against Heresies"

also known as "Adversus haereses", "On the Detection and Overthrow of the So-Called Gnosis"

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Entry tags: Greek, Religious Group, Christian Theology, Christian Traditions, Early Christian Text, Apologetics, Christianity, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Text, Theology text, Classical Indo-European, Orthodox Christianity, Italic, Latinic, Language, Latino-Faliscan, Early Christianity, Indo-European, Western Medieval text, Orthodoxy

Irenaeus of Lyons is one of the most important figures of the Christian Church of the 2nd century. He appears at the end of the second century with the aim to express a new type of literature, the so-called Literature of Tradition, which exceeds Apologetics and marks the beginning of a new, more universal expression of the ecclesiastical body. Where and when Irenaeus was born is not known. His birth cannot even be precisely determined. According to him, during his childhood he was associated with the bishop of Smyrna St. Polycarp. He was probably born in or near the city of Smyrna, in a Christian family. According to St. Jerome, Irenaeus had been a student of Papias of Hierapolis. He studied theology and perhaps the secular *paideia* of his time. It seems however that he had not received a philosophical education. It is certain though that he was well versed in rhetoric. It is not certain when Irenaeus moved to Lyon, yet it seems plausible that this happened around or before 177 CE. The reasons for his settlement there were either ecclesiastical or related with family issues, since Lyon was an important city, with a strong Christian and Greek-speaking element. According to Gregory of Tours, Irenaeus had been sent there by St. Polycarp. Whatever the case may be, it is certain that he had already been ordained as presbyter when he arrived at the French city. A testimony regarding his arrival in Lyon mentions that Irenaeus had welcomed a group of enthusiastic Phrygian Christians, who believed that the second coming of Christ would take place in Lyon, at a time when Pope Eleutherus (ca. 174 - ca. 189) was persistently asked to ratify condemnations against Montanist bishops. At the time of his settlement in Lyon, Montanism movement was in full swing, while at the same time persecution by the Roman authorities was developing. Thus, he immediately begins writing activity, writing to the people of Asia Minor about the ongoing problems, as well as to the Pope of Rome. Assuming his duties as bishop of Lyon in 177 or 178 CE, he launches an intensive project that aims not only to the evangelization of the Greek and Latin speakers, but also of the Celts, expanding his activity as far as southern France and western Germany. He actively fights against the heresies, especially the Gnostics, constantly traveling, founding schools, and writing books. He soon realizes that it is not enough to confront a heretical teaching at the time, but through coordinated reorganization and safeguarding of the teaching of the church. By the time of Irenaeus, a great number of heresies were thriving in the Roman Empire. Particularly in his episcopal see, the teachings of various Gnostic groups arrived through Greek merchants, who had begun an oratorical campaign, teaching that the material world was the accidental creation of an evil god, from which we are to escape by the pursuit of gnosis. Irenaeus argued that the true gnosis is in fact knowledge of Christ, which redeems rather than escapes from bodily existence. Irenaeus therefore set his sights to compile a work, which will not refute any heresy individually, but will expose the teaching of all of them. The result of his effort is the "Against Heresies", a voluminous work of five books. The original, Greek text is lost; only some extensive passages survive. Yet, Irenaeus's opus is known to us through a Latin translation, made sometime before the times of St. Augustine. The translation we possess today comes from about 20 manuscripts, with the oldest dating back to the 9th century. In his prologue, Irenaeus declares his sorrow for the "fall" of Christians into heresies, due to their ignorance. He also declares that his main purpose is to demonstrate the falsity of these heresies. In the first book, the first ten chapters refer to the system of Valentinus; from chapters 11 to chapter 21st Irenaeus discusses the heretic teachings of Secundus, Ptolemy, Mark, and until the end references are made to all the Gnostics known during his

times, as well as some previous ones (Simon the magician, Menander, Saturnilos, Vasileides, Karpocrates, Cyrinth, Ebionites, Nicolaites, Kerdons, Marcion, Tatianus, Varbelians, Ophians, Cainites). In the second book, Irenaeus discusses the theory of God and the world according to the Gnostics, and especially the Valentinians, and provides instructions to his readers on the correct interpretation of the Scriptures. He also refers to the distinction that the Valentinians made between human and divine inspiration. Irenaeus's chief objective in these two books is to expose the faith and the tradition of the Church. In the third book, he refers to what is the Apostolic Tradition of the Church, the Apostles, the Monarchy of God, Christ and ends his discussion with a prayer. The fourth book begins with the discussion on the unity of the Old and the New Testament, the patterns and prophecies found in the books of the Old Testament, as well as the teaching of parables. Finally, in the fifth book, Irenaeus refers to the teaching of the Lord and of the Apostle Paul; the resurrection; the Creator and Father, as witnessed by the words of Jesus himself. This fifth book will eventually become very popular, since almost all of the subsequent Church Fathers, such as Hippolytus of Rome, Tertullian, Clement of Alexandria, etc will cite it in their own writings.

Date Range: 130 CE - 202 CE

Region: Lugdunum

Region tags: Western Europe, Europe, France

Lugdunum (modern day Lyon, in France). The see of st. Irenaeus

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Irenaeus of Lyons: Identifying Christianity, John Behr, Oxford University Press 2013
- Source 2: Irénée de Lyon et les débuts de la bible chrétienne : actes de la journée du 1.VII.2014 à Lyon, Agnès Bastit-Kalinowska, Joseph Verheyden
- Source 3: Contre les hérésies (188), trad. Adelin Rousseau et Louis Doutreleau, Cerf, coll. « Sources chrétiennes » ; Livre I, no 263-264, 2 vol., 1979 ; Livre II, no 293-294, 2 vol., 1982 ; Livre III, no 210-211, 2 vol. : 1974 ; Livre IV, no 100, 1965, 1008 p. ; Livre V, no 152-153, 2 vol., 1969.
- Source 1: Contre les hérésies. Dénonciation et réfutation de la gnose au nom menteur, trad. Adelin Rousseau, Cerf, coll. « Sagesses chrétiennes », 3e éd. 1991
- Source 2: Guillaume Bady et Marie-Laure Chaieb, Irénée de Lyon, théologien de l'unité, Paris, Beauchesne, coll. « Théologie historique » (no 132), 2023
- Source 3: Sara Parvis (éd.) et Paul Foster (éd.), Irenaeus : Life, Scripture, Legacy, Fortress Press, 2012
- Source 1: Marie-Laure Chaieb, Irénée de Lyon : « Contre les hérésies », Éditions du Cerf, 2011.
- Source 2: Eric Osborne, Irenaeus of Lyons, Cambridge University Press, 2001
- Source 3: Jacques Fantino, La Théologie d'Irénée, Paris, Éditions du Cerf, Collection Cogitatio fidei, 1994.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://www.ccel.org/ccel/wace/biodict/biodict/Page_Index.html
- Source 1 Description: Scanned pages available for Dictionary of Christian Biography and Literature to the End of the Sixth Century A.D., with an Account of the Principal Sects and Heresies.
- Source 2 URL: <https://peterkirby.com/taking-irenaeus-seriously.html>
- Source 2 Description: Taking Irenaeus Seriously
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.earlychristianwritings.com/tixeront/section1-4.html#irenaeus>
- Source 3 Description: Handbook of Patrology: St. Irenaeus
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.fondationsaintirenee.org/la-fondation/decouvrez-irenee-de-lyon/>
- Source 1 Description: DÉCOUVREZ IRÉNÉE DE LYON
- Source 2 URL: <http://www.ntcanon.org/irenaeus.shtml>
- Source 2 Description: The Development of the Canon of the New Testament
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.pastortheologians.com/articles/2019/6/13/st-irenaeus-the-beatific-vision-and-the-instrumentalization-of-creation>
- Source 3 Description: St. Irenaeus, the Beatific Vision, and the Instrumentalization of Creation
- Source 1 URL: <https://christianityinhistory.blogspot.com/2007/11/amillennialism-of-irenaeus-ad-120-202.html>
- Source 1 Description: The Amillennialism of Irenaeus

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.earlychristianwritings.com/irenaeus.html>
- Source 1 Description: Irenaeus of Lyons, Against Heresies
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.newadvent.org/fathers/0103.htm>
- Source 2 Description: Against Heresies
- Source 3 URL: <https://remacle.org/bloodwolf/erudits/photius/irenee.htm>
- Source 3 Description: IRENEE, Contre les hérésies
- Source 1 URL: <https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/009025834>
- Source 1 Description: Libros quinque adversus haereses

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Written

 Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Other textile: At the Cambridge University library manuscript 4113 / Papyrus Oxyrhynchus 405 a fragment of Irenaeus's "Against Heresies" is preserved.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: Only fragments of the original Greek text exist, but a complete copy exists in a wooden Latin translation, made shortly after its publication in Greek, and Books IV and V are also present in a literal Armenian translation.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: Nevertheless, the fifth book will become so popular among subsequent Church Fathers, that it had, somehow, initiated the decline of Gnosticism.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although the exact number of the Christians in Lyon, at the times of Irenaeus, is unknown, it is believed that the city had a robust and thriving Christian community. Due to its importance as a strategic location at the convergence of two navigable rivers, Lyon quickly became a natural communications hub. The city became the starting point of main Roman roads in the area, and it quickly became the capital of the province, Gallia Lugdunensis. Hence, many Asiatic Christians arrived there, with strong connections and an almost daily communication with the Orient. A persecution that arose under Marcus Aurelius produced forty-eight, half of them of Greek origin, half Gallo-Roman, martyrs (among others Saint Blandina, and Saint Pothinus, first Bishop of Lyon, sent to Gaul by Saint Polycarp about the middle of the 2nd century).

Reference: Société bibliographique. L'épiscopat Français Depuis Le Concordat Jusqu'à La Séparation (1802-1905). Paris: Librairie des Saints-Pères, 1907.

Reference: Fisquet, Honore. La France Pontificale (gallia Christiana): Metropole De Lyon Et Vienne: Lyon. Paris: Etienne Repos, 1864.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?

– Yes

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– No

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: With his work Irenaeus inaugurates a new type of literature, the so-called Literature of Tradition, which exceeds Apologetics and marks the beginning of a new, more universal expression of the faith of the body of the Church.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Index

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The afterlife, Irenaeus proposed, focuses more on time than space; he looked forward to a time in which humans are fully developed and live the life of God.

Reference: Bretherton, Luke. *Christianity and Contemporary Politics: The Conditions and Possibilities of Faithful Witness*. Oxford: John Wiley & Sons., 2011.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?
– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?
– Yes

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?
– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?
– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?
– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?
– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?
– No

Are formal burials present in the text?
– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?
– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?
– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present
– No

Notes: In fact yes, but only when discussing Gnostic systems. In many Gnostic systems, In Gnosticism, God is known as the Monad, the One. He is the high source of the pleroma, the region of light.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Notes: Only when speaking of Gnostic beliefs. Such pantheon consists of the Aeons. In many Gnostic systems, the aeons are the various emanations of the superior God or Monad.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Book 5 is in fact a defense of the physical resurrection and eternal judgement.

Reference: Wood, A. Skevington. "The Eschatology of Irenaeus". *The Evangelical Quarterly* 41, no. 1 (1969): 30-41.

Reference: Ayroulet, Élie , and Marie Chaieb. "What End of Time? the Eschatology of Irenaeus of Lyon". *Nouvelle Revue Theologique* 143, no. 1 (2021): 34-45. <https://doi.org/10.3917/nrt.431.0034>.

Reference: de Andia, Ysabel . *Homo Vivens. Incorruptibilité Et Divinisation De L'homme Selon Irénée De Lyon*. Paris: Études augustiniennes, 1986.

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– Yes

↳ At some other time [specify]

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world

– No

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– Yes

Notes: Irenaeus' eschatology was based on a literal interpretation of the Bible, especially the Book of Revelation. He believed that there would be 6000 years of suffering before the world ends in a fiery purge. This fire would purify believers ahead of a new human community existing in the New Jerusalem.

↳ Establishment of new political system

– No

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– Field doesn't know

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: According to Irenaeus, everything has been planned by God to help humanity to achieve

spiritual maturity. The world has been intentionally designed by God as a difficult place, where human beings are forced to make moral decisions, as only in this way can they mature as moral agents.

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Field doesn't know

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Optimism/hope
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– Field doesn't know

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– Field doesn't know

Is education gendered according to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

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Reference: Irenaeus of Lyons, "Against Heresies", Hiestand, Gerald. 'passing Beyond the Angels': The Interconnection Between Irenaeus' Account of the Devil and His Doctrine of Creation. Reading: Reading University, 2017.

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